

PEDAGOGY

THE ROLE OF CULTURE WITH HIGH AND LOW CONTEXT IN THE ECONOMY OF SPEECH IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article explores the communication styles within Uzbek culture, highlighting key characteristics and differences from Western norms. Uzbek communication is characterized by indirectness, politeness, and an emphasis on maintaining harmony and preserving face. Non-verbal cues, such as body language and facial expressions, play a significant role in conveying meaning. Collectivism and the importance of personal relationships are integral to Uzbek communication, while conflict avoidance and mediation are preferred over direct confrontation. Understanding these cultural nuances is crucial for effective intercultural communication with Uzbek individuals.

Keywords: Uzbek culture, communication styles, indirectness, politeness, harmony, face-saving, non-verbal communication, collectivism, personal relationships, conflict avoidance.

Introduction. In the context of British culture and its influence on the economy of speech, one can consider the concepts of communication styles with high and low context. These terms refer to the extent to which meaning is conveyed explicitly or implicitly in a given communication setting. Although these concepts are most often associated with cultural analysis, they can also be applied to the economy of speech in British culture.

Communication in a high context relies heavily on implicit understanding, general knowledge, and non-verbal cues. In British culture, there are situations in which communication in a high context prevails, for example: *The British often value politeness and tend to use indirect expressions to convey messages. They may use euphemisms, sarcasm, or subtle hints instead of stating anything directly, especially when discussing sensitive topics or expressing disagreement.*

British speech culture often includes references to common cultural experiences, history, literature, and popular culture. These references presuppose a certain level of basic knowledge, and their understanding contributes to effective communication in a cultural context.

Non-verbal cues such as facial expressions, gestures, and tone of voice play an important role in communicating in a high context. The British can rely on these signals to convey additional meaning or to understand the main purpose of the message. Low-context communication places more emphasis on explicit verbal expression and relies less on general understanding or non-verbal cues. Although British culture tends to demonstrate communication in a high context, in some cases it is possible to observe communication in a low context. In an official or professional environment, British speech culture may be more focused on communication without context. Here, in a professional environment, clarity and accuracy are valued, and messages should be clear and unambiguous. This is especially true in a legal, business or academic environment. Directness, although politeness and non-directness are often appreciated in British culture, there are situations where directness is preferable. For example, in emergency situations or when expressing a firm opinion, a

more direct style of communication may be adopted. Due to the rise of multiculturalism in the UK, interacting with people from different backgrounds may require a clearer communication style to ensure clarity and avoid misunderstandings.

It is important to note that these communication styles exist in a wide range, and people may differ in their preferences and use of communication in a high or low context depending on various factors such as personal background, regional differences and acquaintance with the interlocutor.

Examples can be given of additional aspects that should be considered when studying communication in a high and low context in the speech economy of British culture, such as politeness and indirection: Britons often value politeness and may use indirect expressions to avoid confrontation or insults. This can be seen in phrases such as *“Could you...”* or *“I’m terribly sorry, but...”* rather than in direct requests or statements.

Research methods. Humor and wit. Here we can say that British humor often relies on subtlety, irony and wordplay, which can be considered an important context. Jokes and sarcasm may require an understanding of cultural references, wordplay, or context in order to fully appreciate their intended meaning. Understatement and modesty: British culture tends to value modesty and understatement. People may downplay their achievements, hold back their emotions, or use self-deprecating humor to avoid appearing boastful or arrogant. In addition, you can also talk about negotiations and debates: in formal situations, such as negotiations or debates, a more direct and logical approach can be used to present arguments and counterarguments. Clear and unambiguous communication helps to convey ideas effectively and convincingly. In a society as diverse as the UK, where people from different cultural backgrounds interact, communication without context can be used to provide clarity and understanding. In such situations, a clear explanation of what is happening and the rejection of assumptions about general knowledge becomes crucial. It is also worth noting that individual communication styles can vary, and some people may naturally tend to communicate in a high or

low context, while others may adapt their style depending on the specific context or the people they communicate with.

In general, British culture tends to prefer communication in a high context, emphasizing politeness, indirection and general cultural references. However, there are situations when communication in a low context becomes more noticeable, especially in an official or professional environment and in cross-cultural interaction. The balance between communication styles in a high and low context contributes to the economy of speech in British culture.

It would be useful here to give examples of communication in a high context:

Politeness and indirection:

"I'm sorry, but I'm afraid I can't do it."

"This is an interesting moment. Perhaps we could consider several alternative approaches."

"That's not exactly what I meant, but thanks for the offer."

Humor and wit:

"I told my computer that I needed a byte, and it brought me cookies!"

"I'm not saying I'm Batman. I just want to say that no one has ever seen Batman and me in the same room."

Understatement and modesty:

"I guess I didn't pass the exam so badly."

"It's just a little rain. We are used to it here."

Examples of communication without context:

Clarity and directness:

"Please complete the report by 17:00 tomorrow."

"I do not agree with your proposal because of the potential risks associated with it."

"The train will leave platform 3 in five minutes."

Negotiations and debates:

"Based on the data presented, I propose to increase our marketing budget by 10% in order to achieve better results."

"Your arguments do not take into account the long-term consequences of the proposed policy."

Intercultural interaction:

"Let me explain the process step by step, as it may be different from what you are used to."

"In our culture, it is customary to shake hands at the first meeting."

These examples illustrate that communication in a high context in British culture often involves politeness, indirection, humor and understatement, while communication in a low context emphasizes clarity, directness, negotiation and clear explanations.

And also, let's give additional examples of communication in a high context:

Politeness and indirection:

"I wanted to ask, could you, by any chance, help me with this task?"

"It's a little cool here, isn't it?" (implying a request to adjust the temperature)

"I'm sorry, but I'm afraid I won't be able to attend the event. I have prior commitments."

Cultural features:

"It's like looking for a needle in a haystack" (meaning a difficult task)

"He's a real Sherlock Holmes when it comes to solving problems" (meaning someone's detective skills).

"She's as wise as Dumbledore" (meaning someone's wisdom borrowed from the Harry Potter series)

Non-verbal signals:

A raised eyebrow or a barely noticeable smile indicating agreement or disagreement. Pause before answering to give the other person time to add additional information. Examples of communication in a low context:

Clarity and directness:

"Please send me a report by 15:00 tomorrow"

"I strongly object to this proposal as it is not feasible and sustainable."

"The meeting will take place in Conference Room B on the second floor at 10:00 a.m."

In a professional setting:

Give simple instructions during a training or seminar.

Make brief announcements at an official business meeting.

Give clear recommendations on a project or assignment.

Interaction with representatives of different cultures:

Explain local customs or traditions to representatives of another culture. Use clear language and avoid idiomatic expressions or slang that may be incomprehensible to those who are not familiar with British culture. Specify the time, date and location to ensure effective communication between representatives of different cultures. These examples demonstrate how high-context communication in British culture often relies on politeness, indirection, common cultural references and non-verbal cues, while low-context communication emphasizes clarity, directness, professionalism and clear explanations. The influence of communication in high and low contexts on the economy of speech in British culture may have several consequences:

Efficiency and accuracy: In low-level communication, where clarity and unambiguity are valued, speech economy is aimed at efficient and accurate transmission of information. This can be useful in professional settings such as business negotiations or scientific presentations, where time is often limited and the accuracy of information transmission is crucial. In Uzbek culture, the communication style is usually focused on communication in a high context. Here are a few key aspects to consider:

Indirection and politeness: Uzbek communication often focuses on politeness and indirection. Requests or refusals can be expressed subtly in order to maintain harmony and avoid insults. For example, instead of directly rejecting an invitation, an Uzbek citizen may use expressions such as *"I will try to come"* or *"I will see if I can do it"* to indicate his absence. **Non-verbal communication:** Non-verbal signals play an important role in communication in the Uzbek language. Facial expressions, tone of voice and body language are used to convey emotions, intentions and respect. Maintaining eye contact, nodding, and using appropriate gestures are considered important signs of engagement and respect during a conversation. **Understanding context:**

Communication in Uzbek is largely based on shared cultural knowledge, context, and hidden meaning. Understanding the cultural background and context is crucial to understanding the intended message.

Contextual factors such as social status, age, and the dynamics of the relationship with the interlocutor are taken into account for accurate interpretation of the message. Personal relationships and family values: Personal relationships are of great importance in Uzbek culture, and communication reflects this value. Establishing mutual understanding, maintaining harmony and saving face are priorities in conversations. Respect for elders and reverence for authority figures are common, and communication with them may involve more formal and indirect language. Group orientation and hospitality: Uzbek culture is strongly group-oriented, and communication is often built around collective rather than individual interests. Hospitality is highly appreciated, and meals, drinks, and other forms of hospitality may be offered during conversations. Accepting such offers is considered polite and a way to express appreciation. Cultural traditions and etiquette: Uzbek communication reflects cultural traditions and etiquette. There are certain norms of greeting, introducing and addressing people of different ages or social status. The use of appropriate honorary titles and expressions of respect, such as “mouth” for a qualified master or “*akajon*” for an older brother, is commonplace. The importance of preserving reputation: Preserving reputation is an important aspect of communication in Uzbek culture. People strive to save their own face and not embarrass other people. In public places, criticism or direct confrontation can be avoided to avoid situations that threaten their reputation. Instead, problems can be solved indirectly or privately to preserve harmony. The importance of hospitality: Hospitality is deeply rooted in Uzbek culture. When communicating with guests or female visitors, the hosts often do their best to make them feel welcome and comfortable. Offering food, drinks and engaging in polite conversation is common practice. The guests are expected to kindly accept the hospitality as a sign of respect and appreciation. Respect for elders and hierarchy: Uzbek culture places great emphasis on respect for elders, authority figures and hierarchical relationships.

Young people usually show respect and address the elderly with appropriate addresses such as “*janob/honim*” (sir/madam) or “*otah-onam*” (father/mother-parents) to show respect and acknowledge their seniority.

Non-verbal communication and body language:

Non-verbal communication, including facial expressions, gestures and tone of voice, plays a crucial role in conveying meaning in Uzbek culture. Maintaining eye contact during conversation and listening is considered a sign of attention and respect. A nod and a smile are common gestures indicating understanding and agreement. Indirect communication styles: Uzbek communication often involves indirection and subtlety. Openly expressing disagreement or reporting bad news directly can be seen as impolite or confrontational. Instead, Uzbeks may use mitigating expressions such as polite refusals or delayed responses to convey negative

information in a more indirect way. The importance of personal relationships: Building and maintaining personal relationships is highly valued in Uzbek culture. Trust and familiarity are crucial for effective communication.

By taking time for small talk, asking about family and well-being, and showing genuine interest in other people’s lives, you help to establish and strengthen relationships. The importance of harmony and conflict avoidance: In Uzbek culture, great attention is paid to maintaining harmony and avoiding open conflicts. Disagreements or conflicts can be resolved indirectly or through mediation or compromise. The focus is on finding solutions that preserve relationships and do not lead to disruption in social circles. It is important to note that although contextual communication prevails in Uzbek culture, individuals can adapt their communication style depending on the context and the people they interact with. Moreover, as Uzbekistan becomes more diverse and influenced by globalization, there may be differences in communication styles between generations and regions of the country. Here are some examples illustrating the peculiarities of communication in Uzbek culture:

An example of indirection and politeness: *A friend invites you to a party, but you can’t come.*

Answer: “Thank you for inviting me! I’ll do my best, but I have other things to do this day. I’ll let you know if anything changes.”

An example of how to save face:

Situation: A colleague makes a mistake during a meeting in front of others.

Answer: Instead of pointing out the mistake directly, you could say, “I think there may be a slight oversight in this part. Let’s take another look and make sure everything is correct.”

An example of non-verbal communication:

Situation: You are talking to an Uzbek friend who shares interesting news with you.

Reaction: While listening, you maintain eye contact, nod your head and smile to show that you are involved, interested and supportive.

An example of respect for elders:

Situation: You are addressing an elderly person in a professional setting.

*Answer: You address them using appropriate honorifics such as “*janob/honim*” (sir/madam) or “*otah-onam*” (father/mother-parents) to show respect and acknowledge their seniority.*

Examples of indirect communication styles:

Situation: A colleague asks your opinion about a project idea that you strongly disagree with.

Answer: Instead of directly expressing disagreement, you could say, “This is an interesting approach. I think we should consider all the options and consider different points of view before making a final decision.”

An example of building a personal relationship:

Situation: You meet a new acquaintance at a social event.

Answer: You engage in small talk, ask about their background, family, and interests, showing a sincere interest in getting to know them better.

An example of harmony and conflict avoidance:

Situation: Disagreements arise during a group discussion.

Answer: Instead of getting into a heated argument, you could suggest finding a compromise or offering a different point of view in order to maintain harmony and avoid tension in the group.

Here are some additional examples illustrating how Uzbek communication style may differ from Western norms:

Directness versus Indirection:

The Western norm: In Western cultures, direct and unambiguous communication is often appreciated. People tend to express their thoughts and opinions openly and directly.

Uzbek norm: indirect communication is more common in Uzbek culture. Instead of directly expressing opinions or disagreements, Uzbeks can use hints, subtleties and softening expressions to get their point across. Example:

Western style: "I strongly disagree with your proposal."

Uzbek style: "I understand your point of view, but I have some doubts about this proposal. Perhaps we can consider other options."

Individualism versus Collectivism:

The Western norm: Western cultures often prioritize individualism, where special attention is paid to personal needs and goals.

Uzbek norm: Uzbek culture tends towards collectivism, focusing on the needs and expectations of a group or community. Example:

Western style: "I need to prioritize my own career growth."

Uzbek style: "I would like to think about how this decision will benefit our team and contribute to our collective success."

Personal boundaries:

The Western norm: Western societies often emphasize personal boundaries and respect for privacy.

Uzbek norm: In Uzbek culture, personal boundaries may be more fluid, and greater openness and information exchange are expected. Example:

Western style: "I prefer not to disclose my personal affairs."

Uzbek style: "Let me tell you a little bit about my family and background. We are very friendly, and family is extremely important to me."

Conflict resolution:

The Western norm: Western cultures tend to approach conflict resolution through direct discussion and open confrontation.

Uzbek norm: Uzbeks may prefer to avoid direct confrontation and strive for harmony through mediation, compromise and maintaining social relations. Example:

Western style: "Let's deal with this issue directly and work on solving it."

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that the Uzbek style of communication differs from Western norms in several aspects. Uzbek communication, as a rule, is more indirect, focusing on politeness, saving face and maintaining harmony in social relations. The use of non-verbal cues such as eye contact and body language is important for conveying meaning. Collectivism and group orientation play an important role, with special attention being paid to taking into account the needs and expectations of the wider community. Conflict prevention and mediation are preferable to direct confrontation. These cultural differences in communication reflect the values and norms of Uzbek society, which prioritize respect for elders, hospitality and strong personal relationships. Understanding and adapting to these communication styles are necessary for effective intercultural communication and building positive relationships with Uzbeks.

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